

Ultrasound-assisted degradation of rhodamine B(RhB) organic dye onmagnetic ZnFe₂O₄-ZnS-ZSM-5 nanocomposite catalyst from water media

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Abstract

Magnetic ZnFe₂O₄-ZnS-ZSM-5 zeolite nanocomposite was successfully fabricated using hydrothermal route. The gained nanocomposite was identified via Field emission scanning electron microscopy, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy, magnetic measurements, and Brunauer-Emmette-Teller. The outcomes affirmed the production of ZnFe₂O₄-ZnS-ZSM-5 nanocomposite with the average crystallite size of 14 nm. The aforementioned nanocomposite was utilized as a newly sonocatalyst for the degradation of rhodamine B (RhB) organic dye under ultrasound irradiation. The data revealed complete degradation of RhB (25 mg/L) within 12 min in the presence of ZnFe₂O₄-ZnS-ZSM-5 nanocomposite and H₂O₂ (4 mM). The trapping experiments demonstrated that [•]OH free radicals are the main active species in the degradation of RhB. Furthermore, sonocatalytic performance of the ZnFe₂O₄-ZnS-ZSM-5 nanocomposite was higher than those of raw ZnFe₂O₄ and ZnS, illustrating that the combining ZnS with magnetic ZnFe₂O₄ could be a suitable choice to enhance its sonocatalytic performance. The nanocomposite could be magnetically separated and recycles without any observable change in its structure and activity even after four sequential cycles.

Keywords: ZnFe₂O₄-ZnS-ZSM-5, Zeolite, Nanocomposite, rhodamine B (RhB), Degradation